

THE ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF *CHRYSOLOBALANUS ICACO* AND *THYMUS VULGARIS*: POTENTIAL NATURAL ANTIBIOTICS

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Article Received on 24 April 2026,
Article Revised on 14 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20442509>

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How To Cite This Article: *Jagessar R., Hinds S. (2026). The Antimicrobial Activity of *Chrysolobalanus Icaco* and *Thymus Vulgaris*: Potential Natural Antibiotics. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 15(6), 132–151.

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ABSTRACT

The search for alternative natural antibiotics to replace or compliment synthetic antibiotics is on the increase. This is due to the side effects produced by synthetic drugs, some of which are irreversible and the rise of antimicrobial resistance. The objectives of this research were to investigate the antimicrobial activity of *Chrysolobalanus Icaco* and *Thymus Vulgaris* against selective pathogens and to ultimately develop a natural antimicrobial medication for microbial infections. The Completely Randomised Block Approach (CRBA), consisting of three blocks: Experimental Samples, Control and Reference were used in all cases. The aqueous and ethanolic extract of *Chrysolobalanus Icaco* and *Thymus Vulgaris* were investigated for their antimicrobial activity against selective pathogens, *E.coli*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae* and *C. albicans*, using the Disc Diffusion assay under aseptic conditions. The diameter

of zone of inhibition, DZOI, measured with a rule was used as the indicator of the plant extract antimicrobial activity at a concentration of 0.5g/ml. Experiments were done in triplicates and data were collected after 24 and 48hrs for bacterial and fungal species respectively. Data were analysed for the mean diameter of zone of inhibition (MDZI) with standard deviation, area of zone of inhibition, AZOI and significant differences, in MDZI, between the varying fruit extracts concentrations, using two way ANOVA. For the ethanolic extract of *C.icaco*, the largest DZOI was obtained against *E.coli* (34.25 ± 0.96 mm), whereas the least was obtained against *C.albicans* ($7 \text{ mm} \pm 5 \text{ mm}$). For *T. vulgaris*, the largest DZOI of (23.42 ± 3.0 mm) was obtained for the ethanolic extract against *C. albicans* and the lowest DZOI of (11.25 ± 1.5 mm) was obtained against *S.aureus*. Smaller DZOI were obtained for

the aqueous extracts of both plant parts in comparison to the ethanolic. This range from 11mm to 23.50mm. The combination of both plants ethanolic and aqueous extract showed variation in antimicrobial potency with respect to each plant parts. Selective antimicrobial activity was also evident as *C. icaco* extracts was selective against *E. coli* and *T. vulgaris* was selective against *C. albicans*. The ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *Chrysolobalanus Icaco* (fat poke) and *Thymus Vulgaris (Thyme)* are effective against *E. coli* and *C. albicans* infections. Furthermore, the research addresses the lack of data on the antimicrobial activity of *Chrysolobalanus Icaco* and *Thymus Vulgaris* extracts, in Guyana. The populace are encouraged to continually use *Thymus Vulgaris (Thyme)* as a food seasoning ingredient and the possibility of using the ethanolic extract of *Chrysolobalanus Icaco* as an antibacterial skin and antifungal agent.

KEYWORDS: aqueous and ethanolic extract, *Chrysolobalanus Icaco*, *Thymus Vulgaris*, aseptic conditions, susceptible, standard antibiotics, selective antimicrobial activity and AZOI.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Research in the design and synthesis of antimicrobials will continue to proliferate on our planet, considering that bacteria and fungi develop resistance to antimicrobials over a period of time.^[1-5] This results from indiscriminate use of commercial antimicrobial drugs for the treatment of infectious diseases and the current global antibiotic resistance.^[1-5] Antimicrobial resistance is defined as the resistance against pathogenic microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi.^[6] Increasing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) presents a major threat to public health because it reduces the effectiveness of antimicrobial treatment, leading to increased morbidity, mortality, and health care expenditure.^[7] Bacteria develops antimicrobial resistance via several mechanisms. These include the production of enzymes that will destroy certain prime selective groups in the drug molecule that are necessary for it to act. For example, bacteria produce the enzyme, β -lactamase that will destroy the β -lactam ring of penicillin. The latter is necessary for the antibacterial effect of the drug, penicillin. Other methods bacteria have evolved to protect against the drug, include an increase efflux of the drug across the bacterial membrane, the protection of bacterial ribosomes via processes such as methylation, induced by the enzymes methylase, decrease influx of the drug across bacteria.^[8]

Many synthetic drugs have been used over the years but have several adverse side effects which are usually irreversible when administered and the cost of synthesizing drugs in most cases is an expensive endeavor.^[1-5] Synthetic drugs are also not environmentally friendly. Natural antimicrobials overcome all these problems. Plants have a long therapeutic history over thousands of years and still considered to be promising source of medicine in the traditional health care system.^[9] Plants also have a wide variety of secondary metabolites, some of which are antimicrobial.^[10-12] Crude plants extracts have also demonstrated antimicrobial activity.^[13-15]

Antimicrobial resistance is a global health threat. In 2019, it was responsible for 1.27 million deaths worldwide. Persons of all age groups and regions were affected. However, middle and low income countries were mostly affected.^[16] Drug shortage which is on the increase globally, can exacerbate the spread of drug resistant pathogens like *E. coli* and methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*.^[16] There is no system in place to monitor, and report priority antimicrobial resistant pathogens in Guyana, although one has been drafted.^[17]

Guyana flora is richly diversified and its organic and aqueous extracts have been shown to possess potent and selective antimicrobial activity to date, compared with standard synthetic antibiotics: penicillin, nystatin and ampicillin.^[18-22] The objectives of this research were to determine the antimicrobial properties of the aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *C. icaco* and *T. vulgaris* against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Candida albicans* singly and in combination.

C. icaco is a shrub used largely in folk medicine in the Amazonian region to treat fungal infections.^[23] This plant grows in South Florida, Central America, Northwestern of South America, the Caribbean and tropical West Africa.^[24] Phytochemical screening reveals the presence of flavonoids, quercetin, myricetin, stigmasterol, sitosterol, campesterol, pomolic acid and kaempferol. Also, the presence of anthocyanins and terpenes.^[25-26] *C. icaco* possess anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, analgesic, antidiabetic and anticancer activities.^[27-28]

Thymus vulgaris is used worldwide as a seasoning in cooking and in liquors, in addition to therapeutic use.^[29] The main active agent of *T. vulgaris* is the volatile oil, which has several constituents (such as thymol, γ -terpinene, p-cymene, carvacrol and linalool.^[30] Antibacterial activity of *T. vulgaris* has been reported.^[31-33]

A total of sixteen (16) research articles were reviewed.^[34-49] There is not as much research done on the cocoplum (*Chrysobalanus icaco*) plant.^[34-39] However, some research have been done on the antimicrobial activity of *T. vulgaris*.^[40-49] For *C.icaco*, most of the research articles focused on the antimicrobial activity of leaves and fruit. For *T. vulgaris*, most of the research focused on the essential oil, with a few on the leaves extract.

1.1. Hypothesis of the research

- H_{1a}: Aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Chrysobalanus icaco* and *Chrysobalanus icaco* will show significant antimicrobial activity, supporting their potential as natural antimicrobial agents.
- H_{2a}: There is an equal amount of antimicrobial efficiency between the two plants.
- H₁₀: Aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Chrysobalanus icaco* and *Chrysobalanus icaco* will not show significant antimicrobial activity, refuting their potential as natural antimicrobial agents.
- H₂₀: There is a significant difference between the antimicrobial efficiency of the two plants extracts.

1.2. Research questions

- How effective is the antimicrobial activity exhibited by aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Chrysobalanus icaco* and *Chrysobalanus icaco* against the given pathogens?
- Do they show better antimicrobial properties combined?
- Are there any selective antimicrobial trends ?

2.0. Research methodology

2.0. **Experimental design.** The Completely Randomised Block Approach (CRBA), consisting of three blocks: Experimental Samples, Control and Reference were used in all cases. One block was experimental in nature, whilst another block was the positive control and yet the third block was the negative control.

2.1. Procedure

2.1.1. Preparation of Extracts

2.1.2. Fruit Collection

C. icaco fruits were bought from Bourda and Stabroek markets (in Georgetown) from 3 different vendors. They were weighed, washed and dried (500 grams each) and placed into

glass jars in preparation for each extraction. Likewise, *T.vulgaris* leaves (500grams) were placed in a jar and extracted sequentially with hexane and then ethanol.

2.1.3. Extraction of Ethanolic extracts

The plants were extracted in hexane to remove the fat soluble compounds. 1000mL of hexane was used to just cover the cocoplum and thyme. Extractions was done over a period of three weeks. The hexane was poured into a conical flask. To this was added seven spatula (7) of sodium sulphate and the mixture was then stirred, decanted through a filter paper and into another clean container. Ethanol was added to the plants after the hexane was removed. The plants were extracted in the ethanol then the extract was filtered. Three sequential extractions were done for each plant. The extracts were then filtered and the filtrate removed in *vacuo* to yield viscous oil.

2.1.4. Extraction of Aqueous extracts

For the aqueous extraction, the thyme and cocoplum plants were blended with 1500ml of distilled water. The water was enough to cover both plant materials in a blender. This was done to ensure a high concentration after filtering. After blending, the extracts were filtered using a cloth and the filtrate was stored in bottles in the refrigerator.

2.1.5. Preparation of the media, MHA (Mueller Hinton Agar)

45.6 g of Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) was placed into 1200 ml of distilled water. This was mixed thoroughly then heated with frequent agitation while in a conical flask. The mixture was boiled for one minute to completely dissolve the agar powder, then autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 minutes. The molten agar was poured into 90mm sterile Petri dishes, to a depth of 4mm. These plates were exposed to UV rays for 20 minutes to be sterilized then allowed to cool and refrigerated for use the following day. The plates were dried in a dryer and sterilized with UV rays for 20 minutes before use.

3. Antimicrobial activity

Antimicrobial tests were carried out using the Agar Disc diffusion Method.

3.1. Agar Disc Diffusion Method: (40 plates)

The antimicrobial activity of the crude ethanolic and aqueous extract was determined using the Disc Diffusion method assay. The plates were labeled and inoculated with the respective bacterial colonies. Four (4) discs, impregnated with the antimicrobial plant extracts at

appropriate concentrations were placed on the MHA plates. Separate plates were prepared in a similar manner for the positive and negative controls for the bacterial and fungal strains respectively. The plates containing the bacterial colonies were incubated for 24 hours and 48 hours at 37°C for bacterial and fungal species respectively. It was anticipated that if the extract were antimicrobial, they would diffuse outwards on the agar. Larger the area of zone of inhibition, the greater is the antimicrobial proficiency of the extract. After the required time, the diameter of zone of inhibition was measured, using a ruler. The area of zone of inhibition, AZOI, was computed, from which the antimicrobial proficiency of the extract being evaluated.

3.2. Control Experiment

The control experiment consists of an agar plates which were labeled and inoculated with the respective bacterial and fungal colonies. Four discs, impregnated with the solvents, ethanol and water respectively, were placed on the MHA plates and then incubated for 24 hours and 48 hours at 37°C for bacterial and fungal species respectively. Two Positive control plates for each organism were also made using ciprofloxacin for bacteria and ketoconazole for fungus and were incubated as well. After the required time, the agar plates were examined for zone of inhibition.

It is anticipated that the negative solvent will induce a negligible zone of inhibition while there would be a visible zone if inhibition for the positive control.

3.3. Solutions for antimicrobial studies

A 5% solution of the ethanolic and aqueous extract of each fruit and leaves and combination were made up and were poured into three separate containers. For the aqueous extract, the punched out discs were added to the containers containing the extracts for about one hour and then aseptically transferred with a tweezer to the agar plates (streaked with the microorganism) at equidistant from each other i.e. four discs per plate.

A total of 40 plates were used to assay the fruit extract of *C. icaco* and leaves extract of *T. vulgaris* extracts. Each plate contained four (4) discs. Sixteen (16) plates were used for the positive and negative control. For the positive control, ciprofloxacin and ketoconazole were used for bacteria and fungus respectively.

3.4. Microorganisms used

The human pathogenic microorganisms used for the antimicrobial activity were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, and the fungus *Candida albicans*. All microorganisms were collected from Georgetown Public Hospital, GPHC. All microorganisms obtained were cultured in a Luria-Bertani broth. Luria Bertani broth (LB broth) is a rich medium used to culture bacteria such as *E.coli* and *S. aureus*. It was made by weighing tryptone (10g), yeast extract (5g) and sodium chloride (10g) and placing it in a 1L cylinder. Distilled water was added to make up to the 1L solution and the mixture was poured and re-poured until the contents were dissolved. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.4 using dilute (5%) NaOH. 3mL each of LB broth was placed in test tubes. The tubes were plugged with cotton wool foil and wrapped over each top. The tubes were placed into a beaker and autoclaved at 121 0 C for 2h. These tubes were used in the dilutions experiments.

4.0. RESULTS

Table 1.0: DZOI and AZOI induced by *C. icao* alcoholic and aqueous extract against selected pathogens.

Extract	State of extract	Conc. of extract	Microbes	Diameter of zone of inhibition	Mean Diameter of zone of Inhibition	Area of Zone of Inhibition, AZOI
<i>T.vulgaris</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>C. albicans</i>	13	13.25 ±1.71	137.82
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				11		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				14		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				15		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>C. albicans</i>	21	23.50±3.0	433.52
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				21		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				25		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				27		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>E. coli</i>	0	0±0	0
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>E. coli</i>	21	22 ± 1.23	379.94
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				24		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				22		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				21		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T.vulgaris</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
<i>T.vulgaris</i>				0		

<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				0		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>S. aureus</i>	10	11.25 ± 1.5	99.35
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				12		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				10		
<i>T. vulgaris</i>				13		

Table 2.0: DZOI and AZOI induced by *C.icao* ethanolic and aqueous extract against selected pathogens.

Extract	State of extract	Conc. of extract	Microbes	Diameter of zone of inhibition	Mean Diameter of zone of Inhibition	Area of Zone of Inhibition, AZOI
<i>C.icao</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>C. albicans</i>	11	11.25 ± 0.5	99.35
<i>C.icao</i>				12		
<i>C.icao</i>				11		
<i>C.icao</i>				11		
<i>C.icao</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>C. albicans</i>	8	7 ± 4.76	38.47
<i>C.icao</i>				10		
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>				10		
<i>C.icao</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>E.coli</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>E.coli</i>	35	34.25 ± 0.96	920.85
<i>C.icao</i>				34		
<i>C.icao</i>				33		
<i>C.icao</i>				35		
<i>C.icao</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	11	11 ± 1.4	94.99
<i>C.icao</i>				10		
<i>C.icao</i>				10		
<i>C.icao</i>				13		
<i>C.icao</i>	Aqueous	100%	<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>				0		
<i>C.icao</i>	Ethanol	5%	<i>S. aureus</i>	8	9 ± 1.4	63.59
<i>C.icao</i>				8		
<i>C.icao</i>				11		
<i>C.icao</i>				9		

Table 3.0: DZOI and AZOI induced by combined ethanolic and aqueous extract of *C. icaco* and *T. vulgaris* against selected pathogens.

Extract	State of extract	Conc. of extract	Microbes	Diameter of zone of inhibition	Mean Diameter of zone of Inhibition	Area of Zone of Inhibition, AZOI
Combined	Aqueous	100%	<i>C. albicans</i>	15	14.75 ± 0.5	170.79
Combined				15		
Combined				14		
Combined				15		
Combined	Ethanol	5%	<i>C. albicans</i>	27	23.75 ± 2.75	442.79
Combined				25		
Combined				21		
Combined				22		
Combined	Aqueous	100%	<i>E.coli</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
Combined				0		
Combined				0		
Combined				0		
Combined	Ethanol	5%	<i>E.coli</i>	34	34 ± 0.82	907.46
Combined				35		
Combined				33		
Combined				34		
Combined	Aqueous	100%	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
Combined				0		
Combined				0		
Combined				0		
Combined	Ethanol	5%	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	11	12.25 ± 1.89	117.80
Combined				12		
Combined				15		
Combined				11		
Combined	Aqueous	100%	<i>S.aureus</i>	0	0±0	
Combined				0		
Combined				0		
Combined				0		
Combined	Ethanol	5%	<i>S.aureus</i>	15	11.25 ± 2.63	99.35
Combined				9		
Combined				11		
Combined				10		

Table 4.0: DZOI and AZOI induced by positive and negative controls against selected pathogens.

Extract	State of extract	Conc. of extract	Microbes	Diameter of zone of inhibition	Mean Diameter of zone of Inhibition	Area of Zone of Inhibition, AZOI
Negative Control	Aqueous	100%	<i>C. albicans</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
Negative Control				0		

Negative Control				0	4 ± 4.6	12.56
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control	Ethanol	5%	<i>C.albicans</i>	0		
Negative Control				8		
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				8	0 ± 0	0
Negative Control	Aqueous	100%	<i>E.coli</i>	0		
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				7	5.75 ± 3.95	25.95
Negative Control				7		
Negative Control				9		
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				0		

Table 5.0. DZOI and AZOI induced by positive and negative controls against selected pathogens.

Extract	State of extract	Conc. of extract	Microbes	Diameter of zone of inhibition	Mean Diameter of zone of Inhibition	Area of Zone of Inhibition, AZOI
Negative Control	Aqueous	100%	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	0	0 ± 0	0
				0		
				0		
				0		
Negative Control	Ethanol	5%	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	9	9.25 ± 2.06	67.17
Negative Control				9		
Negative Control				7		
Negative Control				12		
Negative Control	Aqueous	100%	<i>S.aureus</i>	0	0 ± 0	
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control	Ethanol	5%	<i>S.aureus</i>	10	6.25 ± 4.35	30.66
Negative Control				0		
Negative Control				8		
Negative Control				7		

Table 6.0: DZOI and AZOI induced by positive and negative controls against selected pathogens.

Extract	State of extract	Conc. of extract	Microbes	Diameter of zone of inhibition	Mean Diameter of zone of Inhibition	Area of Zone of Inhibition, AZOI
Positive Control	Ethanol	5%	<i>C. albicans</i>	60	59.5 ± 0.71	2779.10
Positive Control				59		
Positive Control	Ethanol	5%	<i>E.coli</i>	59	57 ± 2.83	2550.47

Positive Control				55		
Positive Control	Ethanol	5%	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	35	37 ± 2.83	1074.67
Positive Control				39		
Positive Control	Ethanol	5%	<i>S.aureus</i>	45	46.5 ± 2.12	1697.37
Positive Control				48		

(a)

(b)

Fig.1.0: (a) *C. icaco* ethanolic extract vs *E. coli*. (b) *C. icaco* ethanolic extract vs. Ciprofloxacin.

3. Graphs

This graph shows the overall area of zone of inhibition for the ethanolic extracts. The ethanol extract against *E. coli* had the largest area which is 2249.52 mm².

This graph shows the area of zone of inhibition of the aqueous extracts. The aqueous extracts against *C. albicans* showed the only zone of inhibition.

In this graph, the ethanolic extracts of *T. vulgaris* against *C. albicans* had the highest zone of inhibition. The ethanolic extracts against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and the aqueous extract against *C. albicans* showed zones while the others did not.

In this graph, the ethanolic extracts of *C. icaco* against *E. coli* had the highest inhibition. The ethanolic extracts against *C. albicans*, *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus* and the aqueous extracts against *C. albicans* showed zones of inhibition while the rest did not.

In this graph, the ethanolic extracts of the combined against *E. coli* had the highest inhibition. The ethanolic extracts against *C. albicans*, *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus* and the aqueous extracts against *C. albicans* showed zones of inhibition while the rest did not.

5.0. DISCUSSION

The ethanolic & aqueous extract of *Chrysobalanus icaco* & *T. vulgaris* were investigated for their antimicrobial activity using the Disc Diffusion assay. This technique utilises the diameter of Zone of Inhibition (DZOI) and AZOI, whereby these two parameters are indicators of plant extracts antimicrobial activity. The ethanolic and aqueous extracts were used at a concentration of 5%.

C.icaco ethanolic extract at 5% concentration induced the highest DZOI of 34.25 mm against *E.coli*. The lowest numerical DZOI of 7 mm was induced against *C. albicans*. *T. Vulgaris* ethanolic extract induced the highest DZOI of 23 mm against *C. albicans* and the lowest DZOI of 11.25% against *S. aureus*. The DZOI induced by the aqueous extracts of both plants against the pathogens range from 11 mm to 23.50 mm. Zero DZOI were obtained against *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* & *S. aureus* for both plants.

Both ethanolic & aqueous extracts were combined with the view to amplify antimicrobial potency. The highest DZOI of 34 mm was obtained for the ethanolic combination against *E. coli* & the lowest numerical DZOI of 11.25mm for the alcoholic combination were obtained against *S. aureus*. For the aqueous combination, the highest DZOI of 14.75 mm was obtained against *C. albicans*. The lowest numerical DZOI of zero was obtained against *E.coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus*.

The ethanolic combination resulted in an increase in DZOI against *E.coli* for *T.vulgaris* from 22mm to 34 mm. *T. vulgaris* against *K. pneumoniae*, showed an increase from 0 mm to 12.25mm. *C.icaco* ethanolic extract against *C. albicans* showed an increase from 7mm to 23.75mm and against *K. pneumoniae* from 11mm to 12.25mm. Of the two plant extracts, the ethanolic extract of *C.icaco* produced a higher DZOI of 34.25mm, compared with a DZOI of 22mm induced by *T. vulgaris* extract. The combination resulted in a small increase in DZOI for the aqueous extracts of both plants. *T.vulgaris* against *C. albicans* showed an increase from 13.25 mm to 14.75mm and for *C. icaco*. 11.25mm to 14.75mm. The other DZOI remains the same.

In terms of antimicrobial selectivity, the ethanolic extracts of *T.vulgaris* against *C. albicans* *E.coli* & *S. aureus* were selective over *K. pneumoniae*. However, there wasn't much selectivity amongst *C. albicans*, *E.coli* & *S.aureus* induced by the ethanolic extract. The ethanolic extract of *C. icaco* showed antimicrobial selectivity against *E.coli* over *C. albicans*,

K. pneumoniae and *S. aureus*. The aqueous extract of *T. vulgaris* showed higher selectivity against the five pathogens as DZOI of 13.25mm was obtained against *C. albicans* & zero DZOI was obtained against *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* & *S. aureus*.

The negative control as shown in Tables 4 & 5 exhibit negligible DZOI (5.75mm). However, the solvent ethanol exhibited DZOI of 9.25mm & 6.25mm against *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus* respectively. The positive control Ciprofloxacin and Ketoconazole showed significant DZOI, which are much greater than those induced by the plant extracts, with the exception against *E. coli*. Table 6.0. Fig. 1.0 shows that the DZOI induced by *C. icaco* is not much smaller than that induced by the positive control, Ciprofloxacin. This strongly indicates that *C. icaco* has great potential to develop into an antimicrobial drug.

5.0. CONCLUSION

The antimicrobial activity of *C. icaco* and *T. Vulgaris* were investigated via the Disc Diffusion assay. The *C. icaco* extracts at 5% concentration, induced the highest DZOI against *E. coli* and lowest DZOI against *C. albicans*. *T. vulgaris* ethanolic extract induced the highest DZOI against *C. albicans* and lowest DZOI against *S. aureus*. Smaller DZOI was obtained for the aqueous extract, compared with the ethanolic. The combination of both plants ethanolic and aqueous extracts in most cases resulted in an increase in antimicrobial potency. However, this showed variation. Selective antimicrobial activity was also evident as *C. icaco* was selective against *E. coli* and *T. vulgaris* was selective against *C. albicans*. Thus, ethanolic extract of *C. icaco* and *T. vulgaris* can be used against *E. coli* and *C. albicans* infections in humans.

6.0. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the department of Chemistry for bench space and the department of Biology for the use of equipment to conduct the antimicrobial assay.

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